

STUDY ON TEST METHOD FOR SHEAR PROPERTIES OF SANDWICH CONSTRUCTIONS
OR CORES

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ABSTRACT

The shear properties of sandwich constructions or cores are one of main performance indexes in the design of sandwich construction products. The selection of the test specimen dimensions is studied for the test and the theory in this paper. It is proved that the length-to-thickness ratio of the test specimen $l/h \geq 12$ is reasonable. The scientific conclusion and reasonableness of Chinese State Standard of GB 1455 1 are demonstrated.

TEST RESULTS

1. The test results of the specimen having different dimensions
The shear test results of different length specimen of sandwich constructions having polyurethane foamed core are shown in Table 1 (the thickness of the specimen is 12mm). The shear test results of different thickness specimen are shown in Table 2.

Table 1 The effect of the specimen length on test results

Dimensions of specimen	1(mm)	150		90		60		
	1/h	12		7.5		5		
Shear properties	τ_c		G_c		τ_c		G_c	
Test average value MPa	0.32	4.76	0.27	5.01	0.21	3.11		
Coefficient of variance Cv (%)	5.7	2.8	17.5	2.7	5.8	1.5		

Table 2 The effect of the specimen thickness on test results

Dimensions of specimen	h mm	12	17	15	30	45	60					
	1 mm	150	150	60	60	60	60					
	1/h	12	8.8	4	2	1.3	1					
Shear Properties	τ_c	G_c										
Test average value MPa	0.32	4.47	0.26	3.53	0.22	3.51	0.16	2.93	0.092	2.01	0.056	1.36
Coefficient of variance Cv (%)	4.4	1.5	7.5	2.7	6.8	3.9	4.4	13.8	12.8	10.6	6.3	11.9

THEORETICAL ANALYSIS

In order to determine accurately the shear properties of sandwich constructions or cores, the distribution of the shear stresses in core along the length of specimen should be uniform as far as possible, and the stress caused by additional bending moment should be reduced as lower as possible, so that it may be approaching the pure shear state.

1. The distribution of the shear stress along length of specimen

From the force equilibrium and the deformation compatibility of elements 1*, 2* and 3*, the following differential equation may be obtained finally

$$r_{,xx} - \beta^2 r_x = 0 \quad (1)$$

The distribution of the shear stress along the specimen length may be solved from Eq. (1) as follows:

$$\tau_c = \frac{P\beta \cosh \beta x}{2b \sin \beta l/2} \quad (\text{when single shear})$$

$$\tau_c = \frac{P\beta \cosh \beta x}{4b \sin \beta l/2} \quad (\text{when double shear}) \quad (2)$$

where P is load, b and l are width and length of the specimen, respectively. For the test fixture and the specimen dimensions specified in Chinese State Standard of shear test method (GB 1455) and the shear moduli range (2-300 MPa) of the sandwich construction, the relative errors between the maximum shear stress and the minimum one are

$$\frac{\tau_{\max} - \tau_{\min}}{\tau_{\min}} \times 100 = \begin{matrix} 4.7\% \text{ (when } G_c=300 \text{ MPa)} \\ 0.9\% \text{ (when } G_c=60 \text{ MPa)} \\ 0.03\% \text{ (when } G_c=2 \text{ MPa)} \end{matrix}$$

For ordinary sandwich cores, their shear moduli generally are smaller, but the rigidity of loading steel plate specified in test method of GB 1455 is bigger, hence, β is very small. If the hyperbolic function $\sin h(\beta l/2)$, $\cosh \beta x$ in the formula (2) are spreaded into the series of power function, and taking the first term of the series then the formula (2) will become as follows:

$$\tau_c = \frac{P}{bl} \quad (\text{when single shear})$$

$$\tau_c = \frac{P}{2bl} \quad (\text{when double shear}) \quad (3)$$

The formula (3) is a calculating formula in the test method of GB 1455, and consequently, GB 1455 is reasonable.

2. The stress caused by the additional bending moment of load

When the test specimen of sandwich constructions or cores are tested by shear load in tension and compression, the additional bending moment will be produced because the load apply on the loading steel plates. Due to the normal stress caused by additional bending moment in core, the shear strength of core is reduced. Therefore, it is very important to design reasonably the tested fixture and the specimen dimensions.

The maximum normal stress caused by this additional bending moment in the both ends of the specimen is approximately as follows:

$$\sigma_c = \frac{6M}{bl^2} = \frac{3Ph}{bl^2} \quad (4)$$

Whether honeycomb core or foamed plastic, their strength of compression and shear are all controlled by stability^{2,3}. For the foamed core of polyurethane as shown in Table 1 and 2, they are simultaneously subjected to the stress of compression and shear. According to the criterion of stability under combined stress of axial compression and shear

$$\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_{cr}} + \left(\frac{\tau}{\tau_{cr}}\right)^n = 1 \quad (5)$$

The relation between the shear strength of core and the dimensions of the specimen

may be got finally

$$\tau_c = \tau_{cr} (1-1.92 h/l)^{1/n} \quad (6)$$

According to formula (6), The theoretical value of shear strength are calculated for the cores in Table 1 and 2, and the calculating results are shown in Table 3 (n take 1.5). Thus it can be seen, the calculated results by stability criterion under action of combined stresses are accorded with the test value.

Table 3 Comparison of the theoretical value with test value of the core shear strength

Ratio of specimen dimensions 1/h	12	7.5	5	4
Test value MPa	0.32	0.27	0.21	0.21
Theoretical value MPa	0.34	0.28	0.25	0.23
Relative error (%)	5.9	3.6	16.0	8.7

CONCLUSION

From the results of sandwich construction or core specimens tested by us and theoretical analysis, the following conclusions may be given:

1. Provided the dimensions of the specimens are same and the design of test fixture is reasonable, whether adopting the single and double shear or tension-shear and compression-shear, the difference of test results is less, and their test results may be compared. Therefore, it is reasonable that Chinese State Standard GB 1455 adopts single tension-shear or compression-shear.
2. When the length-to-thickness ratio of the specimen 1/h is smaller, the effect of the specimen dimension on test results is very great. When $1/h \geq 12$, the effect is less, according to calculation of the strength theory of maximum shear, this effect is less than 1%, by calculating of the stability criterion under combined stress, this effect is less than 10%. The theoretical value calculated by the latter is accorded with the test results.
3. Using the test fixture and specimen dimension specified in Chinese State Standard of test method GB 1455, the shear stress distributions along the length of specimen are uniform, and the normal stress caused by additional bending moment is smaller. Therefore, Chinese State Standard of test method GB 1455 is reasonable and scientific. The shear properties determined by this method are more accurate than that determined by flexural one.

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